

Towards FAIR and federated Data Ecosystems for interdisciplinary Research

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Abstract

Scientific data management is at a critical juncture, driven by exponential data growth, increasing cross-domain dependencies, and a severe reproducibility crisis in modern research. Traditional centralized data management approaches are not only struggle with data volume, but also fail to address the fragmentation of research results across domains, hampering scientific reproducibility, and cross-domain collaboration, while raising concerns about data sovereignty and governance. Here we propose a practical framework for FAIR and federated Data Ecosystems that combines decentralized, distributed systems with existing research infrastructure to enable seamless cross-domain collaboration. Based on established patterns from data commons, data meshes, and data spaces, our approach introduces a layered architecture consisting of governance, data, service, and application layers. Our framework preserves domain-specific expertise and control while facilitating data integration through standardized interfaces and semantic enrichment. Key requirements include adaptive metadata management, simplified user interaction, robust security, and transparent data transactions. Our architecture supports both compute-to-data as well as data-to-compute paradigms, implementing a decentralized peer-to-peer network that scales horizontally. By providing both a technical architecture and a governance framework, FAIR and federated Data Ecosystems enables researchers to build on existing work while maintaining control over their data and computing resources, providing a practical path towards an integrated research infrastructure that respects both domain autonomy and interoperability requirements.

Author summary

1 Introduction

The exponential growth of scientific data, coupled with increasing cross-domain dependencies, has created an urgent need for innovative data management solutions [1]. While next-generation sequencing technologies revolutionize genomic research [2], they also highlight a critical challenge: our current infrastructure struggles to handle not just the volume of data, but the complex web of relationships between research outputs across domains. Traditional solutions such as data warehouses, data lakes or even

domain specific repositories, designed for centralized control, are becoming increasingly impractical [3].

This challenge extends beyond mere storage and processing. The reproducibility crisis in modern research [4,5], exacerbated by fragmented data management practices, demands immediate action. While initiatives like the German National Research Data Infrastructure [6], European Open Science Cloud [7], Gaia-X [8] or data commons initiatives, like the Australian Research Data Commons [9] or the NIH Data Commons [10] have begun addressing these challenges, a comprehensive solution remains elusive.

Cloud technologies offer promising capabilities for elastic resource allocation [11], enabling more efficient and sustainable research practices [12,13]. However, relying solely on centralized cloud providers creates new challenges around data sovereignty and privacy. Recent initiatives such as data commons [10] and data spaces [14] demonstrate the potential of distributed approaches aligned with Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles [15]. Yet these solutions often operate in isolation, creating new silos rather than true cross-domain integration.

We propose FAIR and federated Data Ecosystems for interdisciplinary Research (FFDE): a practical framework that combines the benefits of distributed systems with the reality of existing research infrastructure. This approach integrates established domain-specific repositories with support for intermediate research outputs—including experimental data, analysis workflows, and computational results. By providing both the technical architecture and governance framework for cross-domain collaboration, FFDE enable researchers to build upon existing work while maintaining control over their data and computational resources.

This paper outlines the key requirements for such a system and presents a concrete architectural approach to realize this vision. We illustrate how combining proven patterns from data commons, data spaces, and cloud computing can create a foundation for future scientific collaboration—one that respects both the sovereignty of individual research groups and the need for seamless data integration across domains.

2 Drawing from Existing Architectural Patterns

Several architectural patterns have emerged to address different aspects of research data management. Among these, three patterns offer particularly relevant concepts for cross-domain collaboration. Data Commons [10] demonstrate how shared infrastructure can collocate data with computational tools to enable reproducible workflows. The Data Mesh paradigm [16,17] illustrates the value of domain-oriented ownership, treating data as a product and enabling research group autonomy. Data spaces [14] provide frameworks for secure data exchange through standardized interfaces.

FFDE draw from these and other patterns selectively: incorporating shared infrastructure concepts similar to Data Commons, domain-specific governance approaches inspired by Data Mesh, and standardized interfaces comparable to Data Spaces. This combination enables access to existing repositories, incorporation of new data sources, and cross-domain discovery while preserving specialized research practices. By synthesizing proven concepts, we aim to facilitate cross-domain scientific collaboration without compromising the autonomy of individual research communities.

3 FAIR and federated Data Ecosystems

Data spaces offer promising solutions for data sovereignty and governance, yet their adoption in scientific contexts remains limited. Current implementations demand

significant technical expertise and typically focus on specific domains like health, energy, or automotive industries. This domain-specificity, while valuable for industry applications, creates barriers for broader scientific collaboration.

Modern research increasingly transcends traditional domain boundaries. For instance, findings from fluid dynamics can improve weather simulations, which in turn influence agricultural research on resilient plant breeds [18]. As we cannot predict which domains will need to collaborate in the future, research infrastructure must support flexible, cross-domain integration while preserving domain expertise and data sovereignty.

We propose a FAIR and federated Data Ecosystem approach as a foundation for the upcoming generation of research data infrastructure. By combining the governance strengths of Data spaces with practical accessibility, this approach demonstrates how established domain-specific repositories can be integrated with support for unpublished research outputs. The resulting infrastructure accommodates diverse data types, from raw experimental data to intermediate results, analysis procedures, and computational workflows, while preserving domain autonomy.

3.1 Requirements

To enable a scalable, secure, and interoperable domain-agnostic data ecosystems, several key requirements must be addressed. These requirements balance technical capabilities with practical usability while ensuring broad adoption across research communities.

Governance Many domains already have dedicated governance structures that enforce unique rules and standards. The architecture need to accommodate this and allow multiple governance structures to coexist. In addition, a common set of baseline rules must be defined to which all entities must adhere. Clear transparency about the governance paradigms applied have to be communicated, both humanly understandable and machine-actionable. For privacy reasons, this information can be limited to those policies that directly affect public or external access.

Adaptability of Metadata Management The metadata management of data spaces should be adaptable to different scientific domains. While World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [19] standards and well-defined ontologies are ideal, practical constraints often require the separation of technical metadata from semantic metadata. This separation allows data owners full control over their semantics and allows any existing data source to participate. The required technical metadata contains only the core information about who wants to share what data and under what conditions, as well as basic information about how data records are related to each other and where the data is stored.

Simplifying User Interaction Widespread adoption is a primary goal to make the concept of domain-agnostic data ecosystems viable. To achieve this, user interaction must be as frictionless as possible, which can be addressed by facilitating the seamless integration of existing data repositories and by integrating widely accepted interfaces. Technical adapters play a crucial role by transforming various existing data exchange formats into a unified set of well-established and widely recognized standards to ensure ease of use and compliance with FAIR principles.

Data Sovereignty and Security Measures Maximizing data sovereignty means implementing robust technical systems to control access. Advanced security measures such as encryption and continuous monitoring are required to prevent unauthorized

access and data breaches, as well as to comply with data protection regulations such as the European General Data Protection Regulation [20]. All data protection systems should be multi-layered, and the final decision should always be made by data owners. Decentralization plays a critical role in empowering data owners to do this. Ideally, data transfer should take place on a peer-2-peer basis, without central authorities.

Transparency in Data Transactions Systems should provide data owners and consumers with clear visibility into data access, use, and compliance with privacy and ethical standards. Everyone should have a clear understanding of what is happening with their data. This requires a well-established authentication system to ensure that everyone knows who they are dealing with.

3.2 Architectural Components

The following sections outline the key components that form the backbone of our proposed architecture and specify some of the ideas that could be used to realize these components.

Fig 1. Schematic overview of the cloud-based service architecture, illustrating the interplay between data services, application services, governance structures and the underlying data plane. Storage and compute nodes are interconnected with each other through an internal peer-to-peer network and are orchestrated by the cloud management layer; connections are established by adapters.

Governance and Access Control Plane

Decentralized governance operates through distinct community clusters, representing research networks organized by institutional type, research domain, or geographic

region. Each cluster implements standardized data sharing agreements that define common principles for data access, usage rights, and ethical compliance. These agreements establish baseline requirements while preserving flexibility for institutions to implement additional controls based on their specific contexts.

The access control mechanism operates through a chain of digital certificates and policy enforcement points. At the community level, a federated identity management system (such as eduGAIN [21] for academic institutions) validates researcher credentials and institutional affiliations. Data owners then apply granular access controls through attribute-based access control [22] policies, defining permissions based on research purpose and data sensitivity levels.

Inter-institutional trust relationships are formalized through cryptographically signed Memoranda of Understanding, supported by machine-readable Data Usage Agreements in standardized formats like Open Digital Rights Language [23]. This framework allows organizations to establish fast-track approval processes for trusted partners while maintaining comprehensive audit trails.

Data Plane The Data Plane implements a decentralized peer-to-peer network for distributed data management, going beyond existing technologies (like IPFS [24]) by adding rich metadata handling and advanced search capabilities essential for scientific data. It operates through two main components: Data Locations (sovereign storage units spanning multiple platforms) and Compute Nodes (processing resources that connect to existing data sources via standardized adapters). This creates a dynamically interlinked network of data sources that abstracts the underlying complexity from researchers, providing them with a seamless interface to distributed resources.

The architecture supports both compute-to-data and data-to-compute paradigms, optimizing distribution based on various requirements including processing capabilities, storage capacity, network bandwidth, privacy constraints, and geographical location. Nodes within the same domain or organization can establish tighter integration with shared vocabularies and optimized data transfer protocols, while maintaining standardized interfaces for cross-domain interactions. The system scales horizontally - adding new nodes linearly increases storage and processing capacity without central bottlenecks. While decentralized in nature, the infrastructure maintains governance through federated trust domains and standardized policies, allowing organizations to retain full control over their data assets while participating in the broader network.

The network automatically maps relationships between datasets and adapts its topology as nodes join or leave, with built-in location awareness enabling efficient resource allocation and data sovereignty compliance. This flexibility allows research infrastructure providers to easily integrate new storage and compute resources as their needs grow, without disrupting existing workflows or exposing the complexity to end users. The standardized interfaces ensure compatibility across different platforms while preserving each node's autonomy over its data and processing capabilities, creating a truly distributed research data infrastructure that balances openness with institutional control.

Data Service Plane The Data Service Plane transforms the distributed data sources of the data plane into an integrated collection of secondary data resources through automated Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) processes and semantic enrichment. These ETL pipelines continuously extract data from the distributed network, apply necessary transformations for standardization and quality control, and load the processed data into purpose-built secondary databases optimized for specific research queries and domains.

The plane leverages domain-specific ontologies and controlled vocabularies to

168 harmonize data across sources. For example, in life sciences, terminologies like Gene
169 Ontology [25] and Disease Ontology [26] are used to standardize metadata and establish
170 semantic relationships between datasets. This semantic layer enables sophisticated query
171 capabilities and automated inference of relationships between different data elements.

172 While maintaining the distributed Data Plane as the authoritative source of truth,
173 the Data Service Plane creates and maintains specialized secondary databases optimized
174 for common research access patterns. These derived databases significantly improve
175 query performance and data accessibility while ensuring eventual consistency with
176 primary sources through automated synchronization processes. For instance, aggregated
177 genomic variant databases can be automatically updated as new sequencing data
178 becomes available in the distributed network, maintaining a balance between data
179 freshness and query efficiency.

Application Plane 180 The Application Plane leverages both the Data and Service
181 planes to construct sophisticated user-facing interfaces, transforming the distributed
182 infrastructure into accessible research tools. It combines direct access to raw data
183 sources from the Data Plane with optimized secondary databases from the Service
184 Plane to deliver responsive and intuitive research applications. This dual approach
185 enables both high-performance access to preprocessed data and direct exploration of
186 primary sources when needed.

187 This plane implements a diverse set of interfaces to accommodate different user
188 needs and technical expertise levels. These include web-based frontends with interactive
189 data visualization dashboards, data portals, RESTful APIs for programmatic data
190 access, command-line interfaces for batch processing, and plugin frameworks for
191 integration with common tools. By abstracting the underlying distributed architecture
192 behind these familiar interfaces, the plane significantly reduces the technical barrier to
193 entry, allowing researchers to focus on their scientific questions rather than managing
194 distributed systems, data formats, or compute resources, while giving them the option
195 to reference a wide range of data sets from different fields.

4 Conclusion 196

197 The architectural components and requirements outlined in this paper represent
198 essential building blocks for future research data ecosystems. By combining distributed
199 architectures with practical accessibility, we have described an approach that offers a
200 viable path toward true cross-domain scientific collaboration. The proposed layered
201 architecture—comprising governance, data, service, and application planes—provides
202 the necessary flexibility to accommodate diverse research needs while maintaining data
203 sovereignty and security. The strength of this approach lies in its ability to bridge
204 existing domain-specific repositories with emerging collaborative requirements. Rather
205 than replacing established systems, it enhances them through standardized interfaces
206 and semantic enrichment, enabling researchers to leverage both specialized tools and
207 cross-domain capabilities.

208 This acknowledgment highlights the growing importance of breaking down
209 traditional domain boundaries to enable future scientific breakthroughs through data
210 connectivity and analysis. However, realizing this potential depends on the active
211 engagement of the research community. Research institutions should critically assess
212 their existing data infrastructure in relation to the requirements outlined in this paper,
213 identifying gaps and opportunities to strengthen cross-domain collaboration. Domain
214 experts play a crucial role in shaping the foundations for meaningful data integration by
215 contributing their knowledge to the development and refinement of domain-specific
216 ontologies and metadata standards. At the same time, infrastructure providers must

work towards implementing standardized interfaces that adhere to the architectural principles described, ensuring compatibility and seamless integration within the broader research ecosystem. Furthermore, funding bodies have a key responsibility in recognizing the value of cross-domain data sharing and interoperability, actively supporting initiatives that promote the long-term sustainability of an interconnected research landscape. Only through collective effort and commitment can these possibilities be fully realized, paving the way for innovative discoveries and a more integrated approach to scientific inquiry.

The future of scientific research depends on our ability to break down data silos while respecting domain expertise and data sovereignty. The architectural components and requirements presented here provide guidance for achieving this balance, but success relies on widespread adoption and continuous refinement by the research community. The time to act is now—as the volume and complexity of scientific data continue to grow, the need for effective cross-domain collaboration becomes increasingly critical.

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Author contributions

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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